

Thermal Studies of Copolymers of Methylmethacrylate and Acrylic Acid

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Copolymers of methylmethacrylate and acrylic acid have been synthesised by charge-transfer mechanism using a mixture of amine and carbon tetrachloride as initiator in dimethyl sulphoxide at 60°. Percentage yield, molecular weights and reactivity ratios have been evaluated. The copolymers are characterised by ir and ^{13}C nmr spectroscopy. Thermal stabilities are checked by differential scanning calorimetry and thermogravimetric analysis and the properties have been compared with those of the free-radical copolymers. The charge transfer copolymers are easily processable and have comparable thermal stabilities as the free radical copolymers. The thermal stability can be improved by esterification of the acid polymers.

POLYMERISATION of methylmethacrylate (MMA) and acrylic acid (AA) by charge transfer (CT) mechanism using various amines and carbon tetrachloride in dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO) has been extensively studied in this laboratory¹⁻⁴. Copolymerisation of MMA and AA by CT mechanism proceeds with moderate rate. We report here the synthesis, characterisation and thermal studies of CT copolymers along with a comparison of these properties with those of copolymers of MMA/AA produced by conventional initiators.

Experimental

MMA, AA, DMSO, CCl_4 , 2,2'-azobisisobutyronitrile (AIBN), dimethylamine (DMA) and allylamine (AAM) were of analytical grade and purified by standard procedures. Polymerisations were carried out in vacuum ($\approx 10^{-5}$ mm/Hg) and followed dilatometrically¹⁻⁴. The high vacuum system consisted of an oil diffusion pump (Basynt) with an external heating device backed by a rotary pump (Compton Greaves) capable of creating a vacuum of 10^{-5} mm/Hg. The system was connected to an all-glass vacuum lines of wide bored glass (2.5 cm dia) which facilitated efficient degassing. A conventional McLeod gauge Vacuscope was used for measurement of pressure in the system. Pyrex glass was used throughout and all the taps were lubricated with high vacuum silicon grease (Dow Chemicals). The degassing was carried out by freeze-thaw method.

Reactivity ratios (r_1 and r_2) were calculated by Finemann-Ross (FR)⁵ and Kelen-Tüdös (KT)⁷ methods. Molecular weights ($\bar{M}_n$) were obtained viscometrically in chloroform at 30° using Mark-Houwink-Sakurada equation; Huggin's constant, K_2 was 0.40. The values of K and α were computed from osmotic data and found to be 2.9×10^{-2} dl g⁻¹

and 0.285 respectively. The concentrations of the solutions for viscometric experiments were maintained so as to keep the ratio of efflux times for solution and solvent within 1.1 to 1.5. The capillary bore diameter of the Ubbelohde viscometer was 0.4 mm. Since the bore of the capillary being very small and the solvent used was chloroform and the efflux time controlled, the kinetic energy correction could be neglected for practical purposes⁸.

Ir spectra were recorded on a Carl-Zeiss specord 75 IR spectrophotometer, and ^{13}C nmr spectra were recorded by Sophisticated Instruments Facility, Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore, at 67.89 MHz using broad-band proton decoupling. Differential scanning calorimetry (D.S.C.) was done in air with a Mettler TA 3000 instrument at a heating rate of 10°/min. Thermogravimetric analysis (T.G.A.) was carried out using a Perkin-Elmer thermal analyser in air and nitrogen atmosphere at a heating rate of 10°/min.

Results and Discussion

Ir spectral studies and elemental analysis reveal that AAM does not copolymerise with MMA or AA. However, it can be used as an initiator in charge transfer copolymerisation of MMA and AA. In CT copolymerisation with DMA or AAM, the yield and molecular weights ($\bar{M}_n$) increase with the increase in [MMA] in feed until an optimum ratio 7.95 of [MMA]/[AA] is reached. In free-radical copolymerisation of MMA/AA with AIBN initiator, the yield and molecular weights are higher than those in CT method. The lower yield in CT method may be due to neutralisation of the acid monomer with amine. This is supported by the fact that the yield with more basic AAM is lower than the corresponding yield with less basic DMA. The CT

copolymers are, however, easily processable and soluble in a number of organic solvents such as acetone, dioxan and chloroform. On the other hand, the free radical copolymers are not easily processable and are insoluble in common solvents. Thus, the CT polymers are better for the study of copolymer properties. These are less hygroscopic than the free radical polymers.

Reactivity ratios (r_1 and r_2) for the CT copolymers calculated by FR and KT methods are as follows, FR method : $r_1 = 2.00 \pm 0.02$, $r_2 = 0.35 \pm 0.02$ in DMA ; $r_1 = 1.80 \pm 0.02$, $r_2 = 0.48 \pm 0.03$ in AAm ; KT method : $r_1 = 2.05 \pm 0.01$, $r_2 = 0.36 \pm 0.02$ in DMA ; $r_1 = 1.79 \pm 0.05$, $r_2 = 0.47 \pm 0.02$ in AAm. The r_1 and r_2 values of free radical copolymers are 2.02 and 0.11, respectively⁹. Difference in the r values between free radical and CT polymers may be explained as follows. AA forms intermolecular aggregates that include dimer in solution in which the acid and the other components do not associate¹⁰. The amines can disrupt the aggregates of AA thereby increasing r_2 and decreasing r_1 . AA molecules can form weak hydrogen bonds with amine molecules. However, this tendency is not very high because $-N \cdots O-H$ bonds are weaker

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than $O-H \cdots O$ bonds. Therefore, the decrease in r_1 value is not appreciable. Because of the allylic bond in AAm, the nitrogen atom has a higher tendency to donate the electron in comparison to that of DMA, thus r_2 value for AAm is higher than that of DMA.

The ir spectra of the copolymers obtained with high [AA] show a broad peak at $3200-3400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to intramolecular hydrogen bonding. The broad peak is absent from the spectra of copolymers when [AA] is low. At lower concentration of [AA], the AA units in the copolymer are far apart and hence can not form hydrogen bonds. The strong band at 1735 cm^{-1} is for C-H stretch and the medium band at 950 cm^{-1} due to out-of-plane OH deformation of acids.

In the ^{13}C nmr spectra of the copolymers, the low field resonances at $\delta 178.1$, 177.8 and 177.0 correspond to carbonyl carbons. The resonances at $\delta 54.6$ and 52.9 are due to methylene carbons, at $\delta 51.7$ to methoxy carbon, at $\delta 45.2$ and 44.8 to quaternary carbon, at $\delta 41.1$ to methine carbon from AA and at $\delta 16.8-19.0$ to methyl carbons.

Typical D.S.C. thermograms for the copolymers (prepared by AAm initiator) with two feed ratios (1.93 and 5.80) and for pentanol ester of the copolymer with the feed ratio 5.80 are shown in Fig. 1. Temperatures at which the co-polymers, prepared by CT method (AAm and DMA) and free radical method (AIBN) showed transitions are presented in Table 1. The thermograms display three apparent melting endotherms. The initial melting is accompanied by recrystallisation of the polymer as indicated by the return of the thermograms to the baseline¹¹.

Fig 1. D.S.C. thermograms of co-polymers of MMA/AA : (a) feed ratio=1.93, AAm initiator, (b) feed ratio=5.80, AAm initiator and (c) pentanol ester.

TABLE I—D.S.C. DATA OF CO-POLYMERS OF MMA/AA

Mole ratio in feed [MMA]/[AA]	Initiator	Endo peak ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)			Exo peak $^{\circ}\text{C}$
		I	II	III	
1.93	AAm	125	181	288	401
5.80	AAm	118	177	310	410
1.93	DMA	102	120	258	382
5.80	DMA	95	188	268	399
1.93	AIBN	128	165	290	402
5.80	AIBN	115	152	305	412
Pentanol ester					
5.80	AAm	123	186	322	423

The temperature corresponding to the first endothermic peak decreases with the decrease in [AA] in the co-polymer. Decrease of AA content in the co-polymer reduces the initial melting temperature probably due to decreasing tendency to form hydrogen bond. This is supported by the fact that the final melting temperature and the exothermic decomposition temperature increase with the decrease in AA content. Thus, after the initial melting where a portion of the polymer melts, the polymer stability increases with increase in MMA content in the co-polymer. Thermograms of the annealed co polymers (at final melting temperature) do not show the melting endotherms. This indicates that the thermal change at or near fusion temperature is permanent and that some degradation occurs along with melting. The esterified polymers also show three melting endotherms and one decomposition exotherm. The peak temperatures of the endotherms and exotherm for esters are more than those of the corresponding acid polymers. This upward trend of decomposition temperature caused by the esterification of copolymers with higher alcohols may be helpful in preparing thermally stable polymers.

TABLE 2—T.G.A. DATA OF CO-POLYMERS OF MMA/AA

In feed [MMA]/[AA]=1.93, *5.80

Initiator	Atmosphere	IDT ₁ °C	% wt. loss in 1st. stage	IDT ₂ °C	% wt. loss in 2nd. stage	IPDT °C	Temp. at varying % wt. loss (°C)		
							10	20	50
AAM	Air	172.2	14.3	273.5	82.8	278.1	213.1	283.3	300.2
	N ₂	186.4	25.0	362.2	74.2	326.4	240.5	305.8	395.4
DMA	Air	138.6	11.5	236.4	84.0	222.7	179.5	238.6	259.1
	N ₂	142.0	6.9	199.5	79.9	166.9	161.4	172.7	202.7
AIBN	Air	225.0	8.7	268.2	77.4	269.1	261.4	276.1	298.1
	N ₂	156.8	14.6	340.9	76.4	305.5	254.6	326.2	368.4
AAM*	Air	143.0	17.1	283.3	81.9	271.1	228.6	292.8	305.4
	N ₂	152.2	24.2	366.4	73.4	285.2	240.2	325.4	400.5
DMA*	Air	101.0	20.8	281.8	77.8	258.0	156.8	205.2	323.4
	N ₂	110.0	52.1	345.6	47.2	289.3	161.0	205.2	295.5
AIBN*	Air	184.1	10.4	247.7	79.2	252.6	247.1	267.0	290.9
	N ₂	128.7	25.0	322.7	71.5	292.4	177.3	248.2	370.4

From Table 1, it is evident that thermal stabilities of free radical co-polymers prepared with AIBN and CT co-polymers prepared with AAm are similar. However, CT co-polymers from DMA have lower thermal stabilities. This shows that with proper selection of initiator, it may be possible to prepare thermally stable co-polymer by CT method.

Fig. 2 shows typical T.G.A. curves for MMA/AA co-polymers (prepared with AAm initiators) in air and nitrogen atmospheres with two feed ratios (1.93 and 5.80). The T.G.A. data for co-polymers

Fig. 2. Thermogravimetric traces for co-polymers of MMA/AA : (a) feed ratio=1.93, in air, (b) feed ratio=5.80, in air, (c) feed ratio=1.93, in N₂ and (d) feed ratio=5.80, in N₂.

prepared with AAm, DMA and AIBN are presented in Table 2. All the co-polymers decompose in two stages, the major portion being decomposed in the second stage. The decomposition temperatures are determined by the intersection of the tangent to the steepest portion of the T.G.A. curve with its strain-line. The initial decomposition temperature for first stage (IDT₁) increases with the increase

in [AA] in co-polymer. This may be due to hydrogen bonding as discussed earlier. IDT₁ and the extent of first stage degradation for a particular sample is higher when nitrogen atmosphere is used. Thus, the first stage degradation, in which CO, CO₂, CH₃OH etc. may be removed, is initiated by the presence of oxygen in air; but once the degradation starts, the products are more efficiently removed by flow of nitrogen. IDT₁ in case of free radical polymers is higher in air than in nitrogen. Thus, the initial degradation mechanism is not similar in CT and free radical co-polymers. The initial temperature for second stage degradation (IDT₂) is higher when MMA content is higher in the co-polymer. Thus once the intramolecular hydrogen bonds are broken in the initial degradation stage, AA units act as loose points in the co-polymer backbone where degradation is favoured. Integral procedural decomposition temperature (IPDT)^{1,2} is also higher when MMA content is more. It is observed that esterification of the co-polymers imparts better thermal stability to the polymers. Considering the temperatures for a particular weight loss, it is found that around 20% degradation, the co-polymers with higher AA content are more thermally stable, whereas above 20% degradation the copolymers with higher MMA content are more stable.

IPDT is a good datum for thermal stability in T.G.A. For CT co-polymers with AAm initiator, IPDT values are higher than those for free radical co-polymers. Thus CT method can produce co-polymers with higher thermal stability which are also easily processable. It is seen from the data that the second melting endotherm in D.S.C. is accompanied by the initial degradation in T.G.A. Thus the first melting endotherm may indicate the glass transition temperature for the co-polymer.

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